

Crystallization hybrid modeling and simulation in robotic 3D printing of continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites

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Introduction

- The prepreg tapes change their width (and thickness) when heated through the robotic 3D printing nozzle.
- The cut prepreg tapes contains residual stresses.
- Drying may have an effect on the width.
- Crystallization can also contribute to the deformation.
- Experimental DMA tests are used to analyze the deformation during prepregs' heating.
- A hybrid twin model is constructed

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Outline

- 1 Experiments
- 2 Viscoelastic modeling of the prepregs
- 3 Modeling the initial strain release
- 4 Crystallization strains
- 5 Conclusion

Experimental setup

- DMA test with film tensile fixture
- Different heating and cooling rates
- Sufficient time at equilibrium

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- Large steady-state period allowing thermal equilibrium.

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- Cold crystallization started around 145°C
- No cold crystallization during the second heating phase

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- First experiment characterizes the behavior of the prepreg without further crystallization
- Second experiment identifies the crystallization behavior

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Thermal simulation

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K} \nabla T) = 0$$

- The boundary conditions : convection throughout the domain with $h = 25 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$.
- The PGD is used : $T(x, y, z, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n F_i(x, y) G_i(t) Z_i(z)$
- The thermal simulation shows a quasi constant temperature through the thickness of the part at every time step.

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A viscoelastic model

- A Kelvin-Voight viscoelastic model is selected
- Neglecting the acceleration, the equilibrium equations write :

$$\sigma = E\epsilon + \mu\dot{\epsilon}$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\sigma - \sigma_0) = f$$

- The gravity constitutes the body force f .
- The thermal stresses are written as :

$$\sigma_0 = E\alpha\epsilon_0$$

$$\epsilon_0 = \alpha(T - T_0)$$

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- The used mechanical properties have the following form :

$$\mathbf{E} = \begin{bmatrix} E_{11} & E_{12} & E_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_{12} & E_{22} & E_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ E_{12} & E_{23} & E_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & G_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mu_{12} & \mu_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \mu_{12} & \mu_{22} & \mu_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \mu_{12} & \mu_{23} & \mu_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

- The elasticity properties are computed using Halpin-Tsai equations and the available data sheets.
- The unknown parameters \mathbf{P} are identified using the Proper Generalized Decomposition and the optimization.
- The identification is performed only on the experiment reaching up to 120°C.

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Parametric identification

- Optimization cost function :

$$(\mathbf{P}) = \underset{\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{+k}}{\operatorname{arg\,min}} \left\{ \sum_{i=2}^4 \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \left(\bar{\epsilon}_i^{e,j} - \epsilon_i^{s,j} \right)^2 \right) \right\}, \quad (1)$$

- The optimization is performed on the sections 2 to 4 which are the first cooling, second heating and second cooling.
- The translated strains $\bar{\epsilon}_i^{e,j}$ are derived from the experimental strains $\epsilon_i^{e,j}$ such as the final experimental state and simulated ones superpose.
- The extra strains recovered from section 1 (heating 1) are the residual/drying strains

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Initial residual and drying strains

- Residual/drying strains as defined as :

$$\bar{\epsilon}^{ini} = \bar{\epsilon}_1^e - \epsilon_1^s$$

- The identified initial irreversible strain release will be modeled using neural Ordinary Differential equations.

Initial strain release

- The initial irreversible strain ϵ^{ini} release can be generated by residual strains and drying of the prepregs.
- Neural Ordinary Differential Equation (Neural ODE) will be used to identify the strain release.

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon^{ini}}{\partial t} = \mathcal{F}(t, \Delta T_0, \epsilon^{ini}, \epsilon^s)$$

- To guarantee stability, the following stabilized neural ODE formulation is

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon^{ini}}{\partial t} = \epsilon^{ini} \cdot \mathcal{G}(t, \Delta T_0, \epsilon^{ini}, \epsilon^s) + \mathcal{H}(t, \Delta T_0, \epsilon^s)$$

- For stability \mathcal{G} is a neural network imposed to output negative values by construction.

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Neural ODE model

- Training performed over 100 epochs with ADAM algorithm.
- A custom built learning rate update function is used
- the LSTM takes in memory the last two values in the input parameters (t, T, ϵ^s)
- Only the last value of $\bar{\epsilon}^{ini}$ is passed into the next time step

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Converged model

- Absolute errors after convergence :
 - On training region : 0.02% strain
 - On Testing region : 0.07% strain
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Derivative functions

Prediction on the 180C experiment

- The prediction can be performed on the experiment with the temperature increasing up to 180C on section "heating 1".
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Viscoelastic + residual strains model

- The crystallization strains are defined as :

$$\epsilon_{180}^{crys} = \bar{\epsilon}_{180} - \epsilon_{180}^s - \epsilon_{180}^{ini}$$

Correlation with DSC experiment

- The DSC experiment shows an initiation of crystallization around 146.7°C during the first heating phase.
- The strains shows a decrease in value starting 147°C – 148°C.

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Converged model

- Relative error of about 10.92% on both testing and integration
- The neural ODE relied mostly on the the simulated strains
- The thermal differential and time are also important in this case, as the evolution direction in time and temperature is important to create a unique input to the Neural ODE.

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Crystallization effect

- Crystallization can generate further changes in \mathbf{E} and α
- To avoid the need to identify the parameters at every cycle, we build a hybrid model
- The modeling compensate the strains using :

$$\epsilon^{\text{total}}|_{T>147} = \epsilon^{\text{exp}}|_{T>147} - \epsilon^{\text{c}}|_{T>147}$$

- The same Neural ODE used for crystallization is extended throughout the experiment to predict the effect of the crystallization using :

$$\dot{\epsilon}^{\text{total}}|_{T>147} = \dot{\epsilon}^{\text{total}} - \dot{\epsilon}^{\text{c}}(\epsilon^{\text{total}}, T) + \dot{\epsilon}^{\text{c}}(\epsilon^{\text{c}}, T_{\text{c}})$$

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Crystallization model

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Crystallization model

- Final result when accounting for the initial strains and the crystallization effect.

Conclusion

- We can identify the viscoelastic material properties of robotic 3D printed prepregs.
- The effect of drying and residual strains is modeled and used on unseen data.
- The predictions generalize well far beyond the training region.
- The effect of the Crystallization on the strains and material performance is modeled using stabilized Neural ODEs.
- The prediction generalizes outside the training region.
- Stabilized neural ODEs are stable for data applications.

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Spoilers

- Link the material properties to the crystallization percentages and shape.

- The crystals radius, volume, and percentage are post processed from videos.

Thank you for your attention

Crystallization hybrid modeling and simulation in robotic 3D printing of continuous carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites

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